

**Labour Migration in South Asia:
*Shared Features and Common Solutions***

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Abstract

This commentary highlights the common features of migration scenarios of South Asian countries and suggests possibilities of collective interventions, to address the emerging issues in times of COVID-19 pandemic and beyond.

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Introduction

South Asia assumes considerable prominence in the global map of labour migration, as most of the countries in this region (India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Afghanistan, Bhutan and Maldives) are important origins and/or destinations for thousands of migrants, who had to move out of their native lands in search of improved livelihood options.

As per the estimates of United Nations (UN) International Migration Report, 2020, there are 281 million international migrants living outside their countries and a significant per cent of these migrants belong to South Asia (IOM, 2019). There is a widespread presence of people from India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh and Nepal in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries and many other far-off destinations. Further to this, in almost all South Asian countries, greater proportions of migrants are internal migrants, who essentially move only within the borders of their home countries.

In countries like India, Pakistan and Bangladesh, the quantum and proportion of internal migrants are quite high compared to their international counterparts. Intra-regional migration is also quite important in South Asia, as countries like India, Pakistan and Maldives are home to large number of migrants from other countries from within the region.

The stock of migrants from South Asian countries can be broadly divided into two categories: 'distress-driven' and 'choice-based'.

The first set of migrants are the poorer and marginalized, who migrate in search of basic employment and living. The latter category includes those with better set of material and human resources, for whom migration is essentially for upgrading their professional and living standards. For the first category, which is more prominent in the countries of South Asia, migration is often a livelihood strategy, as there are no prospects for employment and basic livelihood options in their own native places. The

ensuing discussion in this commentary focuses more on the latter category, i.e. the poorest and vulnerable-most migrants. An attempt is made to understand the common features of migration scenarios of various countries in South Asia and to discuss some possibilities for improving the plight of migrants in/of the region.

Common Drivers and Shared Traits

Regional disparities, and rural-urban divide is found to be the major driver for employment-induced, internal migration in South Asian countries. With increasing urbanization, many people from South Asian countries are migrating from rural areas to urban centers for better livelihoods. Massive movement of rural poor towards urban centres/capital regions in South Asia (e.g. Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata, Dhaka, Islamabad, Karachi, Kathmandu, Kabul, Colombo, Male', Thimphu) lead to situations where urban areas are overcrowded without basic facilities.

Often, these rural-urban migrants do not get fair and dignified dealings in their destinations. They also become subject to unequal treatment in labour markets and social exclusions in their host-communities. Apart from rural distress, most of the countries in the region have many socio-political tensions, which act as drivers for out-migration. Countries like India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Nepal and Afghanistan had witnessed many episodes of socio-political conflicts, during the past few decades. Many of these conflicts forced large number of people to move out of their homelands, to save their lives and seek basic livelihoods.

Similarly, protracted political tensions in Afghanistan has resulted in a massive exodus of its population to nearby Pakistan and many other countries, within and outside the South Asia. If we go by Global Peace Index, 2020, the South Asian region is currently the second least peaceful region in the world, with

worrying situations of peacefulness in countries like Bhutan, Nepal, Sri Lanka, and Afghanistan (IEP, 2020).

In terms of climate-change induced migration too, countries in the region share considerable similarities. Distress migration of 'climate-refugees' is very prominent in countries like India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Maldives, Nepal and Afghanistan. Maldives is under the threat of getting submerged totally in the near future. Nepal has had many natural calamities and environmental degradation that have forced many to move outside their localities for good.

Apart from these, forced distress-migration has also been frequently happening in various parts of South Asian region due to development induced migration, unplanned urbanization/resource depletion and so on. The case of migration of Chakamas and Hajongs, from Chittagong Hill tracts of present Bangladesh (following landlessness due to development of the Kapati Dam in 1960s) is a striking example for this development-induced migration.

For most of the South Asian countries, rural distress characterized by an intense employment crisis is the main reason for urban-bound migration. Lower levels of labour-absorption capacity of local economies are found pushing the rural poor to move to urban centres. The proportions of seasonal/circular migrants are normally very high among the internal migrants.

These migrants, who have some foothold in rural areas, regularly return to their native places as per the cropping-calendars, to participate in farm activities like harvesting. However, in the recent past, all-over South Asia, the rural employment crisis has considerably worsened, which even adversely affected the rhythms of seasonal and circular migration. There are many manifestations for this deepening rural distress including: increased landlessness, wider spread of indebtedness, mounting number of farmer suicides and so on.

Apropos international migration beyond the regional boundaries, most of the south Asian countries have same destination countries – the major being the GCC countries, where migrant workers from the same region compete with each other for jobs; undercut wages and survive on deplorable working and living conditions.

South Asian countries also show a lot of similarities in terms of the patterns of women's migration. Overall, marriage migration continues to be the main reason for women's migration. Usually, some sort of a hidden labour migration is happening through marriage migration, as many of the poor women ultimately end up entering in the local labour markets after moving with their spouses.

In most of the South Asian countries, patriarchal controls or norms are quite dominant in the migration scenarios. Patriarchal/societal controls are found crucial while deciding migration decisions and in shaping the labour force participation of women. The larger governance framework of migration is also highly influenced by these norms and patriarchal controls. Accordingly, bans, introduction of job restrictions, stipulation of age limits/bars to 'regulate' women's mobility is quite common in South Asian countries.

Due to such restrictions, in countries like Pakistan and Afghanistan, the share of women in migration flows is considerably low. In the case of Sri Lanka, where women migrants outnumber their male counterparts, there are stringent restrictions on women's free movement. A recently introduced family background record system stipulates that women need to obtain a clearance from a designated local official that there are no children in the family who requires the care of the women who intends to migrate. This sort of restrictions leads to a situation where women prefer to choose illegal routes/modes for migration, which *inter alia* leads to many pernicious practices (including trafficking, sexual abuse).

Of late, there is also a visible decline in the supportive framework provided by the states/governments in the region towards migrants. Withdrawal of support systems, rolling back of /lesser allocation on migrant-welfare measures, dilution of protections given vide labour law framework, introduction of stringent and disabling regulations for governing migration and so on are viewed as manifestations for this 'growing prominence of neo-liberal ethos' in the larger governance of labour. As state is an important authority in regulating and facilitating migration as well as for protecting the rights and dignity of the migrants, the overall moving away of state from pro-poor interventions is a cause of worry for migrants.

Impact and Implications of the Pandemic

It is quite evident that COVID-19 pandemic has worsened the insecurities and vulnerability of the migrants in /from South Asia. Due to the unexpected outbreak of the pandemic and the subsequent lockdowns, there have been abundant flows of reverse migration (of both internal and international migrants) in all South Asian countries.

Many of the migrant poor had to return to their natives, leaving behind their belongings and livelihood options in the destinations. Often, these migrants had to undergo considerable miseries and spent huge amounts of money to come back to their origins. Further to this, many of them got stranded either in their destinations or in the borders of their home-countries, due to entry/travel restrictions imposed by various countries.

Large proportions of migrants had already lost their jobs during these days of crisis and many others had to accept salary cuts and deterioration in working and living conditions. Those who had to continue staying/working in their destinations often had to face unequal treatment/ discriminations (vis-à-vis the local population) during the pandemic in terms of access to healthcare,

availability of safely measures, quarantine facilities and so on. Further to this, there were also instances of growing xenophobia or ‘othering the migrants’ in some of the destination countries.

From the viewpoint of South Asian countries, there has been a considerable dip in the flow of remittances, since the outbreak of COVID-19 and the resultant chaos, which will have long term development impacts for all those countries, which bank on remittances as a major source of support. Rehabilitation of returnee-migrants and their integration to productive employment avenues in local economies is a major challenge in most of the labour-sending countries in the region.

Unfortunately, in most of the South Asian countries, there is a visible failure of state mechanism while dealing the issues of returnee-migrants, be it internal, intra-regional or international. It was quite alarming that extant state mechanisms in South Asian countries were not adequate enough to provide some modicum levels of food security, income support, social security or health benefits to their migrant populations. Alongside this, in various parts of South Asia, there have been weakening of democratic struggles and dilution of labour laws/regulations during COVID-19 period.

A large number of international returnee-migrants in South Asian countries are now actively looking for return-passage and reintegration into their erstwhile occupations in foreign destinations, as they cannot afford to stay away from employment for considerable period of time. Similar is the case with a major chunk of internal returnee-migrants too. For many international migrants, returning to destinations is now contingent upon completing the vaccination process, as prescribed by the recruiting country. The scarcity of vaccines in home-countries is also emerging as a major deterrent for the migrants to regain their jobs and livelihoods.

It is quite likely that the work practices followed during the crisis period of pandemic is going to leave many long-lasting

imprints in the migration scene of South Asia. In a situation where work from home and distant-working arrangements are increasingly gaining momentum, the physical migration of migrants back to earlier work is likely to be affected at least for some of the occupations. Furthermore, with the ‘new normal and norms’ surfaced by the pandemic, many manual operations carried out by migrants may get automated, given the possibilities of spread of possibilities of industry 4.0 and using the potentials of artificial intelligence. This will also likely to reduce the employment prospects of the migrants.

Need for Governmental Interventions and Collective Solutions

In the post-COVID era, the economic divide between nations and regions and the rural-urban divides are going to get widened. Accordingly, there can be an increase in terms of xenophobia towards the ‘outsider’/migrants. Given this, it is very important for the governments in the South Asian region to actively work on pro-migration policies, which approaches migration in a right-based perspective.

In a way, the shared features of migration scenes in various South Asian countries provide us certain opportunities for working together and forging common solutions. Given the prominence of South Asia, as the most important source region of labour migration, it is highly desirable to have collective initiatives of South Asian governments to negotiate with migrant-receiving countries like GCC, on the possible terms of smooth reintegration of the migrants, with decent working and living conditions.

Similarly, countries in South Asia can also together ensure dignified return and assimilation of intra-regional migrants, in their respective territories. There should also be more concerned efforts towards promoting migrant rights and right-

based migration by utilizing the provisions of or the protective frameworks of labour laws and signing and honoring relevant international labour conventions.

In order to ensure solidarity in migration matters, first and foremost requirement is to have peace within the region. There are brewing tensions in South Asia right now. Thus, there is a need to establish peace within the region. For instance, in various parts of South Asia, there exists deeply contested issues related to legality/illegality of migrants and citizenship/identity aspects of cross border immigrants. These issues need to be amiably resolved in order to effectively address to promote the rights and labour-standards of migrants.

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